

BENEFITS OF INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE IN GLOBAL WORKPLACE

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Abstract. The article talks about the role of the intercultural competence in a multicultural workplace and studies the benefits of intercultural competence in a global workplaces and business.

Keywords. Competence, cross-cultural competence, internal and external outcomes, empathy, flexibility, adoptability.

Today's global environment is making world even smaller and making our life more difficult than it was even 10 years ago. It has become a necessity for people of different origins and cultures to live in interdependent and communicative space. And the change of cultural boundaries in people's lives leads to a sharp increase in social changes. As a result, in our modern and developed world, the demand for cultural diversity and communication exchanges is constantly increasing. So, all people are living closer together. Our age requires people to have strong knowledge, skills, abilities, and unique attitudes along with positive behaviors. For this reason, achieving global development and facilitating positive relationships and connections depends on intercultural competence. In almost every field - business, education, politics, trade, the presence of intercultural competence is of great importance. Having an intercultural competence is an extremely beneficial. So that people with sufficient knowledge, skills, and qualifications can achieve many more convenience in the international area. We will widely study and discuss the benefits of intercultural competence in global workplace and business. "Intercultural competence is a range of cognitive, affective, and behavioral skills that lead to effective and appropriate communication with people of other

cultures.”¹Intercultural competence helps to avoid different cultural barriers in diverse societies. So, this concept is clearly defined by many scientists. For example, “Intercultural competence is the ability to communicate effectively in cross-cultural situations and to relate appropriately in a variety of cultural contexts.” (Bennett and Bennett 2004)² Or, “Intercultural competencies the ability to develop targeted knowledge, skills and attitudes that lead to visible behavior and communication that are both effective and appropriate in intercultural interactions.” (Deardorff, D. K. 2006)³.

Nowadays, it is natural to work with people who speak different languages, have different beliefs, cultures and cause various misunderstandings, inconveniences and disputes during the work process. Working in a culturally diverse place can pose a number of challenges for both employers and employees. They may face a lot of problems. But having intercultural competence totally helps them to overcome obstacles.

Typically, intercultural competence has two types of outcomes. They are internal and external. Internal outcomes include empathy, flexibility and adaptability resulting from the acquisition of sufficient knowledge and skills. External outcomes refer to intercultural communication behaviors that are the result of attitudes, knowledge, and skills. In order to persevere during the challenging times, good leaders and managers are always needed in business. That's why every worker should develop and cultivate new skills that are vital and crucial in modern international workplace. One of the skills that workers should gain is empathy. Empathic employees have the ability to create a positive work environment that fosters growth and productivity. Empathy an ability of putting yourself in someone else's shoes as well as understand other people. So, you will be

¹Internet site:

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Competence_\(human_resources\)#:~:text=The%20term%20%22competence%22%20first%20appeared,Planning%20the%20Executi](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Competence_(human_resources)#:~:text=The%20term%20%22competence%22%20first%20appeared,Planning%20the%20Executi)

²Internet site: <https://www.commisceo-global.com/blog/10-definitions-of-intercultural-competence>

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able to understand their thoughts, feelings, opinions. This helps to create friendly environment. Empathy allows you to behave more kindly and empathize with your partner or co-worker with different culture or background. In addition, you can make many friends and cement your friendships at work by understanding their feelings, emotions, beliefs and behavior. Asking any partner for help if you need would be really helpful and time-saving. Because solving a problem or trying to learn something new on your own may take months to get there. Also, empathy is important in developing communication skills. Being able to communicate effectively with various people plays a huge role in personal and professional development. Empathy in the workplace promotes positive communication and relationships between colleagues, strengthens your bonds, and facilitates the exchange of experiences. Empathy is an important skill that leaders need to make more productive and effective space.

Practicing empathy with a work group can:

- Improve communication. While using suitable tone of voice and body language, showing positive emotions in conversation helps to show your respect and friendship towards your partner. Both employers and employees can achieve a lot of success while having an effective communication.

- Increases creative thinking. For example, you can find different innovations, methods, projects, and easier solutions to problems by knowing and supporting the opinions and worldviews of your colleagues.

- Improves customer service. Empathy in service helps the employee to get to know the client closely, to fully study his wishes and desires, to listen and appreciate him, to establish a long lasting and strong relationship, cooperation with the client.

- Strengthens relationships. Empathy also helps to create a completely free, calm, peaceful and harmonious work atmosphere by gaining the trust of others.

Next one is flexibility. Flexibility in the workplace helps employers and employees to regulate and balance working conditions among different people. This helps to maintain work-life balance and increase productivity. Today,

employees can choose their convenient workplace and working hours in order to increase their flexibility. In the international workplace, individuals need to be flexible and adoptable because there are different nationalities, different conditions and laws. There are 2 ways of making workplaces more flexible:

1. Implementation of flexible work order. It is possible to ensure the development, quality and freedom of work by establishing a flexible work schedule for employees.

2. Regulation of personal flexibility. Between the employer and the employees based on the needs and interests of all, the announcement of rewards or penalties will help to ensure general harmony in the workplace.

The last one is adoptability. Adaptability is the ability to learn new skills and behaviors to meet the challenges of changing environments. In a global workplace, adoptable employees can quickly find their place. Because adoptable people are considered to have the ability to easily accept and overcome problems, changes and difficult situations that arise in the workplace, and to quickly get used to new conditions. For example, changes in the working conditions caused by the global pandemic. Remote working was very difficult for some employees, because many of them did not have enough knowledge and skills to use cutting-edge technologies. In addition, adapting to work with people of different cultures, views, and beliefs is a vivid example of this. In order to achieve adaptability in the global working area individuals need to support 4 common tips.

1. Promote a collaborative culture. A collaborative culture supports diversity and diverse values that converge among colleagues. For example, we can see it in teamwork in modern companies. In this way, they adapt to each other's personality, work style, and culture.

2. Welcome ideas. Workers of diverse cultures and backgrounds may have different opinions, perspectives, worldviews and ideas. So respecting each other in a team, welcoming brand new ideas would perfectly lead in a success.

3. Communicate and connect. Communication is the most important factor of adaptability. In order to create a successful working environment, it is

necessary to have an open and polite attitude towards everyone, to be able to understand representatives of other nationalities.

4. Recruit and attract the right people. It is important to find candidates who are suitable for the company and possess sufficient knowledge, skills, qualifications, and experience. Successful companies always search for people with high level and skills. They also strive to preserve diversity among employees and create a unique work environment that improves morale, creativity, and productivity. For this reason, global business professionals are required to have excellent cross-cultural competence as they work with partners and colleagues all around the world. In order to be successful and effective in their work, people must have deep knowledge and experience about intercultural relations, communication, time, types of verbal and non-verbal communication, and distance between people.

Today's international workplace requires hiring candidates with cross-cultural skills and teaching existing employees these skills. In the case of various companies, it plays an important role in working with customers without difficulties, expanding mutual relations, improving trade relations and business experience. An inclusive team that demonstrates good cross-cultural competence creates a fun, free, competitive, qualitative and healthy work environment. This is the key to personal development and success of not only the company or leader, but also the employee. Having self-respect, value, reputation in the team inspires and motivates the worker even more. People also want to work where there is an atmosphere of friendliness, respect for other cultures and opportunity. Many international corporations in the world are always looking for professionals who are competent, flexible and able to succeed on an international scale, who work with courtesy and sensitivity in business management. Therefore, there are many benefits of having intercultural competence at the individual level.

A clear example of intercultural competence among workers can be seen in their politeness. Different cultures have different attitudes towards politeness. What is considered polite in one country may seem rude in another. That is why it is necessary to have special knowledge in this regard. For example, it is appropriate

to present a business card to your Japanese business partner with it upright and held out in your hand. In Japanese culture it is considered as the sign of respect. In Western culture, you would place business cards on the table and invite your partner to take one of them. In addition, when receiving business papers from your Japanese partner, it is required to read them carefully immediately without putting them in your bag. Intercultural competence is beneficial in knowing and using the taboo topics of conversation as well. For example, when meeting a Ukrainian colleague, you can easily ask about his income and marital status. But it is considered very rude because the representatives of Great Britain and the United States consider it a personal matter.

In current years, working with customers, colleagues, suppliers, partners from different cultures is very popular. Individuals with deep knowledge and awareness of other people's cultures have a higher chance of being hired, while leaders and workers with these skills are at the peak of their success and are more productive and profitable than others. Thus, having intercultural competence ensures becoming a valuable member of the company and strengthening their position in the organization. It creates a wide range of opportunities for each frame and helps to be productive, economical, time-saving, effective, positive, conflict-free and stress-free in the work process.

Books:

1. Raymond Hull (1919-1985), Canadian playwright, Source: <http://www.answers.com/topic/competency> quoted from different source in: Helen SPENCER-OATEY and Peter FRANKLIN (2009), p. 50
2. *Maaleki, Ali (9 April 2018). The ARZESH Competency Model : Appraisal & Development Manager's Competency Model. Lambert Academic Publishing. p. 18*
3. Internet site: <https://www.commisceo-global.com/blog/10-definitions-of-intercultural-competence>
4. Internet site: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.836372/full>